

Place and Landscape: Socio-spatial practices in the Curriculum of the city of Duque de Caxias- Brazil.

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ABSTRACT: *The comprehension about the socio-spatial practices of students permits to dialogue with the point of view that provides to work through constantly experiences with them. Thus, this research analysis how the study of city/urban contributes to former the concepts and school geographic contents using for this the analysis of socio-spatial practices of students of Education for Young and Adults in the municipality of Duque of Caxias in the city of Rio de Janeiro. It is important that themes related to the conception of city/urban be addressed in the curriculum to encourage the developing of socio-spatial awareness of citizen of Duque de Caxias. Methodologically, this works uses a methodology that explores the socio-spatial practices of students, because it is something known and experienced by them. Thus, the educator may uses the reality of students in order to explore their everyday. The teaching of Geography permits that discussions like these in this work be possible, because understand your own city, the social production, the urban issues and your right as citizen are relevant themes to the discipline of school Geography, all these question permits that students recognize themselves within the spatiality of their city. The results of this works shows that the most of students has many difficulties related to interpretation, concepts and geographic contents, as well as the lack of knowledge of their rights as citizens and residents of the city.*

KEYWORDS -*Education of Young and Adults, Teaching of Geography, Socio-spatial practices.*

I. INTRODUCTION

The present work aims to present the context of the basic and public education of the city of Duque de Caxias. The municipality is peripheral and is located in the Baixada Fluminense, which is a region that needs social investments.

Duque de Caxias is considered a very enriching field of research because has an important economic role within the context of the state of Rio de Janeiro and because it is considered a Metropolitan Region according to (Simões, 2015).

This work has as target audience students of Education for Young and Adults because they are subjects that live in city/urban since the moment they leave their houses, passing through many paths of the city that influence directly in the dynamic and the structure of space.

Thus, the study of the city related to the curriculum contents, must be considered a political issue, which means that study the city is a way for citizens to seek their rights. For this, is necessary understand the daily events by means of the critical to bourgeois society and its space.

It is also important analysis the society, the space where are produced the relationship which is established between society and nature by the different societies and their actions in different spaces and scales, because this action permits the reflection so that the student feels an integral part of this construction, that is present in their everyday, in the concrete reality, and that can be observed by them in their socio-spatial practice.

The teaching of Geography has a relevant role in this study because assists the analysis of spatiality in the intellectual formation of students, because permits and develops a critical and spatial thought of different places.

The geography was once considered a memorization discipline also a discipline of description of geographic elements, these conceptions remains in some schools. Because of these ideas, this work aims to overcome these difficulties to show how the discipline is capable to developing a disciplinary knowledge in a reflexive way.

A form de minimizing the difficulties related to Geography is to transform it into a practice of daily life, however it is important to emphasize that not all content can be experienced. Because of this, a critical perspective it is important in a classroom. The curriculum proposal of the discipline of Geography should include the contents and concepts that stimulate the developing of the reasoning and spatiality and that value students as the main subjects of the learning/ teaching process.

Methodologically this work used a case study that investigate in a particular way a certain situation. Thus, the complexity of the problem was empirically analyzed in a unitary way, based on its interpretations, data collection and other information. In this case study was researched the school called Municipal School Expedicionário Aquino de Araújo and the Municipal School Professor Oneres Nunes Oliveira, both located in the district of the City of Duque de Caxias.

In this article, the school of Duque de Caxias was presented as a space of contradictory relationships between the significant economic developing and the socials frailties that reflected within the educational scope. Because of that, this work presents the urban reality that is considered unequal and poorly structured.

Developing the geographic school knowledge through the conceptions of city and urban is a way to make it meaningful of signs and symbols which are spatialized in everyday practices and in the lived spaces by students.

The study of city permits the discussion about everyday spatiality of individuals, their way of life, of economic production, cultural, environmental, social in which the student is inserted. The everyday life of many students are based in their socio-spatial practices which is in this research developing from the workshops in the municipally schools of Duque de Caxias.

II. RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

In this academic research was used as methodology the case study. This kind of investigation is being increasingly disseminated in the Social Sciences, in which Sociology and Anthropology stand out as pioneers from the late nineteenth and early twentieth centuries.

The case study in the area of Education arose in the 1960s and 1970s as the descriptive analysis of unit, which means a school, a classroom and a teacher. Several authors dedicated to case study like Luke (2013), Meirinhos and Osório (2010), Deus, Cunha and Maciel (2010) and André (2009), besides the methodological process of Yin (2005).

The case study is a relevant methodology to educational issues because depending on the approach of the researcher permits understand a real situation from a specific unit.

Because the case study permits the analysis of a specific situation, this work used the case study to analysis two schools by own investigation and procedures to diagnose a real situation. First, the diagnosed situation was detailed and the research was initiated. After the case study was possible found something that until that was unknown and even confirm possible suspicions.

In this research, the school is the study area and the students of Education to Young and Adults are the investigated subjects. The first instrument of research was the analysis of the interpretation of curricular structure from the city of Duque de Caxias, this is necessary to understand the scientific contents and concepts that was applied to target audience in other words the subjects of the research.

To conduct the research was important to know the students so was used workshops and questionnaires as instruments of research. In this research will be discuss the results from workshops, these results are important to think about the socio-spatial practices from students.

In this research was analyzed the Elementary Education in the fourth stage, which attends the sixth and seventh year and fifth stage, which attends the eighth and ninth years. The students in this segment are at least 16 years old.

In the Municipal School Professor Oneres Nunes de Oliveira 10 students participated of the research, with age between 16 and 17 years old, only one student was 54 years old. In the Municipal School Expedicionário Aquino de Araújo the frequency was positive because 24 students participated of the workshops, these students had age of between 16 and 17 years old, only one student was 18 years old and another student was 19 years old (Fig. 1).

Figure 1: Students filling out questionnaires at Scholl Municipal Professor Oneres Nunes de Oliveira (Duque de Caxias-Rio de Janeiro-Brazil).

Source: Camila Vianna de Souza (2017).

III. DUQUE DE CAXIAS AND IT SPATIAL REALITY: THE CONTEXT OF RESEARCHED SCHOOLS

The city of Duque de Caxias has an interesting geographic position because is a municipality that presents an economic wealth very meaningful however the municipality has socials issues very worrying. Therefore, this work will show how the inequalities are distributed in the municipal.

Duque de Caxias is located in the Metropolitan Region of the State of Rio de Janeiro in the Baixada Fluminense, according to The Brazilian Institute of Social and Economic Analysis (2005) the municipality has an area of 442 square kilometers corresponding to 6,8% of the total area of the Metropolitan region of Rio de Janeiro.

According to The Brazilian Institute of Social and Economic Analysis, the municipality of Duque de Caxias has a population 855.046 inhabitants and is territorial division into four districts: 1° district – Duque de Caxias (41 square kilometers); 2° District - Campos Elíseos (98 square kilometers); 3° District – Imbariê (64 square kilometers) and 4° District – Xerém (239 square kilometers) (Fig.2).

Figure 2: Localization of Duque de Caxias, Rio de Janeiro, Brazil.

Source: Organize to Vinicius Seabra.

The first school is located in the neighborhood Parque Felicidade next to the slum called Vila Operária considered a risk area. The school presents a difficulty related to the public transportation because it has only one transportation next to the institution, because of this fact many people have to walk around 10 to 15 minutes to get to school.

The school was founded on September 20, 1956 but was transferred to the Village São Luís in 1956, attending the three shifts: Elementary School of the first and second segments (first to the ninth year) in the morning; the second segment of Fundamental II (sixth to ninth year) in the afternoon, and at night, the specificity of Young and Adult Education only with IV and V stages.

Because of its localization, next to the first district, the school is next to the Washington Luis road, next to the Linha Vermelha and Avenida Brasil.

The first two districts of the city present a degree of uncontrolled urbanization, population densification, little afforestation, being considered as islands of heat. On the other hand, the two other districts have a very small number of residents and buildings, so the temperatures are milder, also because it is located next to the Serra dos Órgãos and an area with lot concentration of green area.

The spatial relationship of Duque de Caxias is complex because presents a dense space of many commercial and industrial relationships such as a peripheral city, but also have different realities as asphalt in contrast to the slums, expansive rents in contrast of inadequate housing and Unit of conservation area in contrast to lack of afforestation.

In terms of economic issues, the city of Duque de Caxias presents a developing economy and occupies the second position in relation to state, losing only to the capital of the state. It is important to emphasize that the Refinery Duque de Caxias that in 1961 became one of the most important industrial poles it is responsible for the significant part of the gross domestic product of the municipality.

It is important to emphasize that the Duque de Caxias is a city where workers leave the Municipality in the morning or at dawn, they face intense traffic and long hours of bottling, mostly in public transport without any comfort, in the direction of the center of Rio de Janeiro, south zone, north zone and west zone, localities considered not so close to Baixada Fluminense, and these workers only returns at night to sleep.

In relation to the historical context in terms of occupation process and space production, the city of Duque de Caxias has marked characteristics in relation to economic, social and political articulation. Simões (2015, 53) explain that: “this metropolization led to an organization of space based on a clear territorial division of labor and a clear process of social segregation [...]”.

The socio-spatial segregation is well demarcated in Duque de Caxias, and there have been some specific cases in the city that have been registered, such as the Metropolitan Landfill of Rio de Janeiro, which will be discussed in more detail later. The neighborhood where the landfill was inserted is located in the first district, known as Jardim Gramacho and is a totally devalued area.

Because of this, the municipality of Duque de Caxias has a significant lack in relation to social basic issues like piped water, adequate lighting, lack of security and mainly due to the strong presence of traffic, and the lack of public health posts, including treating the diseases caused by activities in the landfill. There are still issues related to the environment, which has suffered with constant neglect, dusty, pollution of the nearby rivers, contamination of the water table, among other examples.

In relation to the urban space of the city, there are deterioration of spaces, the destruction of countless areas, the poor being removed from the most central areas of the city, which has become a field of disputes, in a complex reality where few can afford (Simões, 2011, 311).

The dispute for the urban ground permits the process of appreciation of the areas as much the companies as the residential areas and properties with very elevated values, which represents a social selection of the public that will be able to pay for this venture.

The urban ground in a contradictory way is being shaped and restructured, with neighborhoods considered devalued losing its population and social function because are reformed besides receive real estate investments like occur in cases like in the Arco Metropolitano do Rio de Janeiro¹.

In the city is possible to notice that still have many residents who are in poor conditions of locality, housing, structure and this makes us understand how there is a very apparent uneven issue.

This fact only proves the existing social inequality and the lack of investment of the city. Besides, there is also the issue of socio-spatial segregation, where residents end up occupying environmentally vulnerable areas, and depending on the locality, still suffer from pollution problems, bad smell of rivers, heavy amount of waste due to difficulties in the removal of waste and they still face sites that are unsuitable for housing and lack urban infrastructure.

This situation reinforces that the municipality presents an environmentally precariousness besides the lack of adequate supervision and monitoring of some areas to avoid problems.

¹ Construction of a motorway with the purpose of diverting heavy vehicular traffic to reduce the congestion of the main access roads to the city.

IV. EDUCATION OF YOUNG AND ADULTS AND THE CURRICULAR RELATIONSHIP IN SCHOOL GEOGRAPHY: CONCEPTS OF PLACE AND LANDSCAPE

The city and the urban are curricular contents which can bring not only the understanding of social production and space but also the affective relations, identity, socio-spatial practices according to Couto (2014, 2015); Moreira (2017) and of the right to the city as discussed by (Lefebvre, 2001).

Thus, such themes and contents should be discussed in the school environment, in order to enrich the lessons of geography attributing meaning and attracting the students to work with what is theirs, lived by them and built by them, that is, produced and reproduced by those who inhabit or spend their day in the city, exercising multiple relationships in urban space.

It is in the city and urban that spatial forms are experienced in everyday situations and in the Education for Young and Adults is important to discuss and makes them content of the classroom as well as the relation of work since most of the students are traveling to the metropolis. So why not think of content that works the geographical categories, the daily problematization, and the spatial phenomena that are present in the cities?

Thinking the city in its multiple dimensions is to bring knowledge to the Education of Young and Adults, reflecting on it critically, in order to problematize the daily situations, and to build a student with a more reflective thought.

The construction of citizenship is in line with what is being worked out, like the city / urban themes. Therefore, they must present socio-spatial meanings, fomenting their relations, conflicts and crises.

The city has a relation with the social production and with the culture of the people who inhabit it. For this reason, we understand the importance of a critical curricular reading of what will be worked in class.

The Official Document used by Duque de Caxias (2012) does not explicitly present the contents that make reference to the local reality, so it is up to the teacher to make this correlation, using texts, data, facts, information about the daily life, so that the students perceive that there is a relation of what is learned in school with their experiences.

The geography has appropriated of themes linked to city and urban performing analyzes of a certain reality focused on the spatial relationship from the geographic space, because of that, this discussion is important to the teaching.

The developing of the teaching of geography aim the learning of the students attaching importance to the knowledge, experiences, the meanings that students bring to the classroom and what they construct in it. Because of these aspects, it is important to explore the everyday concepts in order for scientific to be introduced (Santos, E. 2008).

Teaching geography is more than contents, it is necessary an autonomy relationship with is relevant to teaching, it's important that the teaching of geography being consistent with the objectives of school discipline, through a harmonious curricular proposal. Geography as science or school discipline appropriates to the concepts that addresses a particular category and two of them are the concepts of place and landscape.

The concept of place can be explored from three analyzes. In the historical-dialectical conception, the place is related to the globalization issue. According to (Cavalcanti, 2013, 90) "The globalization indicates a contradictory tension between the homogenization of the various spheres of social life and fragmentation, differentiation and social antagonisms". To reflect about globalization is analyzing the places, the individualities of a global form as a process that that cannot be understood by itself.

Globalization can produce inequalities, manifestation, impacts even transform the different places from their materiality. About that, (Cavalcanti, 2013, 90) explains: "In the same way the resistance to the phenomenon of globalization e its consequence are performed".

The conception of place has several interpretations. According to Cavalcanti (2013), the place is analyzed from the deconstruction of the totality and the reason to the comprehension of reality.

Lefebvre (1999) works with the place that is in movement, that goes from the lived to the conceived until arriving at the perceived one. In short, the concept of place is related to the lived space, experienced and of belonging.

This study considers the conception of place with the meaning of affectivity, which is part of the daily routine, of the everyday life of the people and it is the point of view that the students can express with the issue of bond and belonging.

In the historical-dialectic conceptions and postmodern the analysis of places is from the transformation and the processes resulting of globalization, homogenization, materiality and totality. Thus, the student needs perceive the different conceptions of scientific knowledge that is a same concept may have different meanings.

The conception of landscape also is presents in this work that according to the Traditional Geography was very important to the theorists who analyzed the concept from the relationship between man and the environment, being characterized by the differentiation of areas, both to seek individuality of places, as well as for the laws of regularity in various localities.

In the new geography, the method of analysis presented by the Traditional Geography is criticized since it shared the idea of observation and description of landscape. The news analysis method were called of theoretical and quantitative and aimed understand the structure of the elements and how these processes work and respond to different spaces.

Related to the conception of landscape, Physical Geography and the Geography start working with the concept of landscape, both with different approaches. For the first one the elements and interactions act on the landscape, while for the second the individual organizes and guides his perception from what he observes in his surroundings.

Nowadays, the conception of landscape according to (Santos, 1988, p. 61) would be: "Everything that we see, what our vision reaches is landscape. Landscape can be defined as the domain of the visible, that which the sight reaches. It is not made up of volume, but also of colors, movements, odors, sounds, etc. "The author still points out in the book *The Nature of Space* (2008) that people work more because of social production.

Santos (2004) defines landscape as the sum of several times. Thus, the landscape is beyond the natural scope, because it also shares the perception of what is perceived, subjective, which is materialized in space/time.

The idea is to show the students that the conception of landscape should be worked not only from the physical aspects, but also from the reproductions of the productive forces, attending to different social functions. According to Cavalcanti (2013) it is understood that the landscape is heterogeneous, it can be constructed and deconstructed, it is the mark of a historical and cultural process of the transformations, of the technique; can have different functions, spatiality and temporality, being modified, adding or not values and functions. According to (Cavalcanti, 2013, 100), "Landscape in this sense reveals not only the production relations of society, structure of society, but also reveals the social imaginary, beliefs, values, feelings of people who construct it".

The construction of geographic reasoning is important for the analysis and construction of time-space relationships, forming citizens capable of understanding phenomena and processes that at first appear to be fragmented.

From the concepts of landscape and place is possible the understanding of the everyday. The discussion of the city will be well grounded if it goes through the proposed scientific concepts (place and landscape) by the Teaching of Geography, together with the socio-spatial practices, because it becomes a reading of the world, of life, of geographical spaces, based on what is experienced by students, and this kind of knowledge is very enriching in class.

In this sense, one can start from the complexity of the particularities through the socio-spatial practices of the students and the city where they live, building scientific knowledge, for example, to understand different phenomena and events that are in different spatial arrangements, showing that different situations can occur in differentiated spaces.

V. SOCIO-SPATIAL PRACTICES AND THE TEACHING OF GEOGRAPHY IN THE EDUCATION FOR YOUNG AND ADULTS

The curriculum of the school geography is composed of numerous topics and contents however it is opted to discuss how the socio-spatial practices of students can be relevant instruments for the understanding of their daily reality, showing with this, that school education can be reflexive to from what is taught.

Every day the student travels a route in the city, which means he moves from one place to the other, whether by public transport, by foot, by car, making a geographical route. In this context, he observes landscapes, buildings, bridges, rivers, avenues, highways, among many other examples.

These paths are marked by a spatiality, by different places, of the coming and going, and therefore, we seek to approach socio-spatial practices in the context of the classroom. According to (Couto, 2014, s.p): "Socio-spatial practices are part of the relationship between man and environment and the struggle for survival."

This means that socio-spatial practices can be understood as the trajectories that individuals make daily in their daily lives and the ways in which they organize themselves to survive. From these practices, the individual acquires experiences, can make comparisons, experiments, abstractions, because the experiences facilitate the understanding of the daily life of the citizen.

With the incorporation of everyday practices in the classroom, geographic knowledge becomes more apparent in order to observe the systematization of empirical knowledge and even the scientific knowledge that will be presented from the discipline of Geography.

It is important to emphasize that when geographic knowledge becomes meaningful, the discipline of Geography can be a powerful tool in the construction of science. It is possible to understand that the experience, the observation of what is around, the places, the analysis and reflection of geographic space are important approaches for the building of a science that works with the interaction between the human beings and the environment. The relationships with the lived space, conceived and perceived presents are meaningful for example to the everyday struggles.

The actions of socio-spatial practices are instruments that help us to understand the geography of the empirical, spaces, places and cities that can become theory if they are worked in the classroom as a form of prior knowledge, to achieve future results in the transformation of these data and information in scientific knowledge.

The daily life of the students of Education for young people and adults is based on their socio-spatial practices, in their daily displacements that have been acquired over time. These students, who are mostly workers, carry with them baggage with rich information about the relation of labor, the productive and exploratory chains and the capitalist system itself.

The concept of socio-spatial practice, according to Couto (2014; 2015),(Moreira, 2017) is related to the existing processes in the spaces, covering both the problems and the conflicts and solutions that are present in the city.

Social practices and spatial knowledge permits to students to better understand scientific concepts, because from their everyday relationship is created a transition movement of abstract thought to concrete, which means from the theoretical thoughts to the day-by-day knowledge.

Wake up early not to "miss" public transportation, which is usually crowded and has no comfort, work eight hours a day, return home in the same conditions as before, arrive in your city, go home or even to school to finish studies, eating at school, but specifically dining, and then being in the classroom, makes the student have a vast baggage of life, the city, the spaces, even if that reading is not critical.

Because of these issues, geography is part of daily life, even if individuals can not perceive, from their routine with flows, circulation, landscape, mobility, work in industry, commerce, the countryside, among others.

Geography exists when one observes the map of the city, or if one has contact with different landscapes; when analyzing the social, environmental and economic impacts of a new industry, among other examples.

Teaching from this relation work X socio-spatial practices X school is a very significant form of insertion of contents and scientific concepts so that the knowledge goes beyond the classroom, that is, a knowledge that is practical, that gives the students the understanding of what it is to be a citizen, how to fight

and claim their rights, how to participate actively in the question of where they live, fight for improvements, among other examples, which are attitudes and behaviors of those who live the socio-spatial practice.

The socio-spatial practices are in the relations of the day to day, in the daily struggle of the man with the environment, with the nature, with the daily life. From his experiences, man is able to make choices, mediate, intervene, analyze, question, position himself, and these actions are fomented in his practices.

Reflecting about every day is to think of the geographic space, the relationships built and existing from what is seen, perceived and lived. The knowledges that are acquired throughout life serve as interactions and representations of a society that reproduces its spatiality in different contexts and temporalities. For Moreira (2017, 27), "space practice is the instrument of every building. The needs of life are the driving force of practice space. The same as saying of space practices as moving responses from human life needs".

It is important to think that spatial practices can be interpreted in different ways, and therefore it is relevant to understand that each experience, place, or landscape can bring a different meaning, or even that reality is similar, each individual analyzes from his perception.

The worker who lives in a certain peripheral area of the city, for example, to move to his work needs to use two to three types of public transport, that is, obviously this does not have the same routine as a moving business owner in your car.

Therefore, the perception of the spaces will be different even by the form of displacement, since the worker has the possibility to observe better what is around him, while the owner of the company is attentive to the traffic, to the direction, however, that does not mean perceptions and analyzes will be based on criticality.

The construction of a mental map, for example, is one of the representations of what the student understands and assimilates in a certain way. This leads us to understand that its starting point differs from that of another student, and so it will be with the recognition of the points that will be highlighted in the map: its limitations, the delimitations of spaces and their configurations (Moreira, 2017).

Socio-spatial practices are also empirical actions that may be contained in school geography classes, since their perceptions, representations, identities, interpretations may be relevant to the understanding of geographic concepts that seek to work the spatiality.

The city of Duque de Caxias can be thought from the concepts of space, place and landscape, which are categories highlighted throughout this study. Thinking about socio-spatial practices to work on the most theoretical concepts already highlighted is a way of approaching a geographical dynamic of what students experience and that may or may not be noticeable.

This movement of approach to concepts also means reflecting on the concrete world, the thought world, the reality world of those who express themselves and build their spatial praxis. It is also a way to maintain the greater participation of the students through the dialogue of the socio-spatial practices, since their experiences will enrich the classes and will be of great importance to extend the knowledge, that is, of the previous ones for the scientists.

The activities for the Education for Young and Adults should be differentiated as the students are resuming their studies for some reason. It is necessary that there be stimulation and motivation so that the students do not give up again finishing their studies. In addition, the importance of dialogue, which serves not only to get to know the students, but also to the development of the language and the encouragement of socialization among the members of the class.

Understanding and patience with this audience is important, since many of them may present difficulties in adapting, understanding the contents that will be taught, as well as exercising their ability to express opinions and express their doubts and feelings. It is important to create spaces for dialogue so that students have the opportunity to exchange experiences, talk, listen, think, and express themselves in a general way.

Most of the activities applied in the Education for Young and Adults need to be consistent with the students' experiences, that is, linked to their reality, so that the students can realize and understand the proposal.

Geography classes, when developed in an uncritical and passive way, do not present pertinent discussions of the contemporary world, of productive work relations, of the problematization of the social

production of space, can be discouraging for the learning process, since the students of the Education for Young and Adults experience this reality daily (Santos, E. 2008).

Thus, the teaching-learning process becomes relevant so that the student is motivated to be in the classroom. With this, it is possible to develop meaningful learning, which has already been envisaged in this study, but as a way of valuing the educational and pedagogical process that will be presented to this student.

Therefore, it is necessary to ask: why do not develop didactic activities in the discipline of Geography from the world of work, being this a way to dialogue with the reality lived through the students' own reports, as Resende (1986) developed in his book *The geography of the student worker*.

Also, why not build mental maps from the socio-spatial practices of the students of the Education for Young and Adults, to analyze and discuss the knowledge of the experiences and to problematize them? These activities would help the student worker to understand how meaningful in the city. These experiences can also contribute to the development of individual and collective conceptions of how much the citizen is able to analyze and perceive school geography as a practice to everyday life.

The construction of geographic knowledge in the Education for Young and Adults needs to be based on a pedagogical and curricular proposal that encompasses contents and themes that facilitate the development of a reflexive discipline, being motivating the process of meaningful learning.

It is important to bring to the classroom activities that will make students feel challenged within the discipline of Geography, such as the interpretation of tables, maps, graphs and to make comparisons between landscapes. All this represents a way of assisting learners in the development of critical and cognitive thinking.

VI. SEARCH RESULTS

From the workshops, it was concluded that in order to teach, it is necessary to organize the material that will be used, to elaborate the contents and concepts present in the curricular proposal, didactic in the execution of the activities, so that the student can develop in a critical way the broaden your knowledge. As already pointed out, it is important that the curriculum of the Education for Young and Adults of Duque de Caxias undergoes a rupture, adapting the contents to the audience it serves.

The accomplishment of this practical research, even having been in two distinct municipal schools, presented similar results. The workshops were applied in the ninth grade classes, of Elementary School II, and it was notorious that many students presented difficulties in writing, in the articulation of thought; as well as problems of interpretation and punctuation perceptible during the writing of the essay and the letter.

Another interest point from what was observed and analyzed in the results of the questionnaires and the interviews was that the issue of the city of Duque de Caxias and of the Baixada Fluminense was not much discussed. During the workshops, it was noticed that the students showed interest in the subject, having doubts, and still actively participating in the proposed activities, encouraged by meaningful learning. Thus, there is no adaptation of content for the Education for Young and Adults and Adults, students simply attend classes on the continents, but do not debate the problems of their own city. In the classes, the Brazilian regionalizations work, but the students do not understand about the Baixada Fluminense, its location, the reason for that name.

The students study the Brazilian population dynamics, but their own socio-spatial practices are not discussed into the classroom. According to Moreira (2017, 27.) "Everything in human life begins and is resolved in space practices. Activity that occurs within the scope of the man-nature relationship, at the moment and collage of the search for man to provide livelihoods in contact with the natural sources of the environment environment, the environmental practice, and from there they unfold to become autonomous in practices social, political, cultural."

In view of this, it is important to discuss socio-spatial practices into the interior of Geography, because the discipline can enable students to discuss the problems they face in their daily life, which until recently were not understood as part of geographic knowledge.

So why not study the school environment, the river the students call *valão*, that when it rains, it overflows? Why not bring the urban problems of the student's city, that is, social, economic, cultural, political

and historical issues of the lived space of the student and resident of the city? Could it be that in this way the construction of thought would not be motivated by meaningful learning?

Therefore, if the questions of the local reality of the student from Baixada Fluminense are not worked on, neither does he remember to bring socio-spatial practices into the classroom. Students are already in class at night, exhausted from a routine of work and chaotic traffic, of the city's recurring urban problems. So why not stimulate learning that has meaning for everyday life? What is the curriculum that does not prioritize the socio-spatial practices, the daily life and the place of the students?

It is understood, then, that this curriculum is the theoretical one, presented in this study previously, available to the teachers of the Education for Young and Adults and that probably is followed, since it presents the objectives of the discipline of Geography, besides the competences directed to Regular Fundamental Education II.

The Education for Young and Adults curriculum could work more meaningful geographic content for the students, that is, that sought to articulate concepts and themes that promote the construction of knowledge articulated with the socio-spatial practices of the same.

However, in the construction of the curriculum there is a matrix for competence that is linked to skills, that is, knowledge in a more mechanized way. In this way, it is understood that the production of the curriculum would have to focus mainly on the phenomena, contents and geographic concepts that directed the reading of the world of the students.

The contents of the subject of Geography should include themes that value the knowledge of the experience and the lived space, since these categories can be important starting points for the construction of a conceptual class. For Santos, E. (2008, 146): "[...] the choice and development of the generating theme from the thematic universe of the students requires spatial knowledge that relates the place to the global, that is, impose a perspective who sees the world through the articulation of scales of analysis".

However, it is understood that there is a contradiction in the content presented to the Education for Young and Adults, that is, an inconsistency in the proposal. It is necessary to reinvent, reinterpret and rework a geography that is capable of embracing new knowledge for this modality.

In this sense, it is important that there is a proximity between educator and student, in which the presented contents are brought in a more playful and dynamic, the classes are more expositive, with images of the daily life, so that debates and discussions are generated, that conventional ways of teaching Geography are only for more theoretical content.

Thus, students can feel part of the process of knowledge construction and in this way, it will be possible to dynamize also what will be presented to the class. A proposal for a differentiated activity in the Education for Young and Adults, based on what was analyzed in the workshops, allowing students reflection, geographic reasoning and discussions, is based on their daily life and their socio-spatial practices, as a stimulus for the construction of knowledge and learning, (Couto, 2014).

Therefore, reflecting on the curriculum being proposed for the Education for Young and Adults is fundamental, as the students at many moments in the workshop have shown interest in knowing their own history, and also excited to bring possible solutions to the city's urban problems, such as residents and students, generating pertinent debates and discussions that were well used, including for the insertion of new concepts, such as the right to the city and socio-spatial practices.

VII. CONCLUSIONS

The city of Duque de Caxias presents itself as a place full of lives and stories, of people facing different urban problems in the spaces to survive. In addition to these, daily struggles that are already part of this scenario, as the numerous strikes, demonstrations in the city for a better quality of life.

The curricular document could highlight in the introduction of the text about the discipline Geography, the relevance of working with the contents from the socio-spatial practices of the students. In this way, it would be possible to reinforce the need to articulate between the teacher's pedagogical practice and theory and practice.

Therefore, it is the responsibility of the teacher to bring certain contents that enable students to understand their reality, with examples of their city and their lived space.

Therefore, it is believed that education must be critical, so that students can understand themselves as part of society and the processes of transformation that occur in the city, and the teacher has the possibility to approach everyday reality in their classes, showing the importance of problematization, dialogue and reflection.

Therefore, it is relevant to understand the socio-spatial practices of Education for Young and Adults to reflect on meaningful learning, that is, to enable students to discuss their routine, their daily life, their reality, from their spatialities, which can be an important stimulus for the teaching-learning process.

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